

O‘ZGARUVCHI TARTIBLI KAPUTO-FABRITSIO OPERATORI ISHTIROK ETGAN DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN CHEGARAVIY MASALA

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Annotatsiya.

Ushbu ishda vaqt o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha o‘zgaruvchi tartibli Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori, fazoviy o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha esa Lejandr operatori qatnashgan xususiy hosilali differensial tenglama uchun lokal shartli masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan. Bunda Lejandr polinomlarining xossalariidan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar.

O‘zgaruvchi tartibli Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori; Lejandr polinoplari; Furiye usuli.

BOUNDARY PROBLEM DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION WITH CAPUTO- FABRIZIO OPERATOR OF VARIABLE ORDER

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Abstract.

In this work a unique solvability of nonlocal boundary problem for partial differential equation involving Caputo-Fabrizio operator of variable order in time and Legendre operator in space-variable. Properties of Legendre polynomials have been used.

Keywords.

Caputo-Fabrizio operator; Legendre polynomials; Fourier method.

Ushbu ishda o‘zgaruvchi tartibli Kaputo-Fabrizio operatori qatnashgan to‘lqin tenglamasi uchun bir chegaraviy masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishini tadqiq etamiz.

Masalaning qo‘yilishi. Shunday $U(x,t) \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap C^2(\Omega)$ funksiya topilsinki, u $\Omega = \{(x,t) : -1 < x < 1, 0 < t < T\}$ sohada

$${}^C D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)} U = [(1-x^2)U_x]_x + f(x,t) \quad (1)$$

tenglamani va

$$U(x,0) = \varphi(x), \quad -1 \leq x \leq 1 \quad U_t(x,0) = \psi(x), \quad -1 < x < 1 \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi, hamda $x = -1, x = 1$ da $U(x,t), U_x(x,t)$ chegaralangan bo'lsin.

Bu yerda

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)}U = \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} \int_0^t e^{\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}(t-s)} U''(s) ds, \quad 1 < \alpha(t) < 2 \quad (3)$$

$\alpha(t)$ o'zgaruvchi kasr tartibli Kaputo-Fabritsio operatori [1], $B(\alpha(t))$ normallashtiruvchi funksiya bo'lib, $B(0) = B(1) = 1$ shartni qanoatlantiradi. $f(x,t), \varphi(x), \psi(x)$ funksiyalar esa berilgan funksiyalar bo'lib, $\varphi(0) = 0, \varphi(1) = 0$.

Masalaning yechilishi. Dastlab $f(x,t) \equiv 0$ bo'lgan holda (1) tenglamaning yechimini $U(x,t) = \nu(t) \cdot X(x) \neq 0$ ko'rinishda qidiramiz. U holda (1) dan

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)}\nu(t) \cdot X(x) = [(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x)]\nu(t)$$

ni olamiz. Bu tenglikni $\nu(t) \cdot X(x)$ ga bo'lsak

$$\frac{{}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)}\nu(t)}{\nu(t)} = \frac{[(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x)]}{X(x)} = -\lambda.$$

yoki

$${}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)}\nu(t) + \lambda\nu(t) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$(1-x^2)X''(x) - 2xX'(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0 \quad (5)$$

tenglamalar kelib chiqadi. $U(x,t), U_x(x,t)$ funksiyalarning $x = -1, x = 1$ da chegaralangan yechimga ega ekanligi ma'lum hamda bu yechim

$$X(x) = P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2^n \cdot n!} \cdot \frac{d^n(x^2-1)^n}{dx^n} \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots) \quad (6)$$

Lejandr polinomlari orqali ifodalanadi [2].

Ma'lumki [2], $P_n(x)$ ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) Lejandr polinomlari $[-1;1]$ da ortogonal sistema tashkil qiladi va $\|P_n(x)\|^2 = \frac{2}{2n+1}$.

Ihtiyoriy $[-1;1]$ da bo'lakli uzlukli $g(x)$ funksiyani $\{P_n(x)\}$ sistema bo'yicha Furye qatoriga yoyish mumkin [2]:

$$g(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n P_n(x), \quad C_n = \frac{(g, P_n)}{\|P_n\|^2} = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 g(x) P_n(x) dx.$$

Bunday qatorlarni Furye-Lejandr qatorlari deyiladi.

Masala yechimini Furye-Lejandr qatori ko'rinishida qidiramiz:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} V_n(t) P_n(x), \tag{7}$$

bu yerda $V_n(t)$ hozircha noma'lum funksiyalar.

Berilgan funksiyalar $f(x, t), \varphi(x), \psi(x)$ larni ham Furrye-Lejandr qatoriga yoyamiz:

$$f(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(t) P_n(x), \tag{8}$$

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varphi_n P_n(x), \quad \psi(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \psi_n P_n(x),$$

(9)

bu yerda

$$f_n(t) = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 f(x, t) P_n(x) dx, \quad \varphi_n = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \varphi(x) P_n(x) dx,$$

$$\psi_n = \frac{2n+1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x) P_n(x) dx.$$

(8) va (9) ni (1) va (2) ga qo'yish natijasida quyidagi Koshi masalasiga ega bo'lamiz:

$${}^C D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)} V_n(t) + n(n+1) V_n(t) = f_n(t), \tag{10}$$

$$V_n(0) = \varphi_n, \quad V_n'(0) = \psi_n. \tag{11}$$

Bu yerda ψ_n va φ_n lar mos ravishda $\psi(x)$ va $\varphi(x)$ funksiyalarning Furrye-Lejandr koefitsiyentlari.

(10) tenglamaning operator qatnashgan qismini soddalashtiramiz.

$$\begin{aligned} {}^C D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)} V_n(t) &= \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} \int_0^t e^{\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}(t-s)} V_n''(s) ds = \\ &= \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}t} \int_0^t e^{\frac{1-\alpha(t)}{2-\alpha(t)}s} V_n''(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

$M(\alpha(t)) = \frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}$ belgilash kiritsak, oxirgi tenglik ushbu ko'rinishni oladi:

$${}^C D_{0t}^{\alpha(t)} V_n(t) = \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \int_0^t e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n''(s) ds.$$

Endi bu tenglikdagi integralni soddalashtiramiz. Bo'laklab integrallash qoidasini qo'llasak,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_k''(s) ds &= V_n'(s) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} \Big|_0^t + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n'(s) ds = \\ &= V_n'(t) e^{-M(\alpha(t))} - V_n'(0) + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n'(s) ds = \\ &= V_n'(t) e^{-M(\alpha(t))} - \psi_n + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n'(s) ds \end{aligned}$$

tenglik hosil bo'ladi.

U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \int_0^t e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n''(s) ds &= \\ = \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \left(V_n'(t) e^{-M(\alpha(t))} - \psi_n + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n'(s) ds \right) &= \\ = \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} V_n'(t) - \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} + \\ + \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) e^{-M(\alpha(t))s} V_n'(s) ds &= \\ = \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} V_n'(t) - \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} + \\ + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))(t-s)} V_n'(s) ds ; \end{aligned}$$

Tenglamada qatnashgan $n(n+1)V_n(t)$ ifodani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz:

$$n(n+1)V_k(t) = n(n+1) \int_0^t V_n'(s) ds + n(n+1)V_n(0)$$

Hosil qilingan tengliklarni (10) tenglamaga olib borib qo'yamiz. Natijada tenglama quyidagicha ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} V_n'(t) - \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} + \\ + \int_0^t M(\alpha(t)) \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))(t-s)} V_n'(s) ds + n(n+1) \int_0^t V_n'(s) ds + n(n+1)\varphi_n = f_n(t) \\ \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} V_n'(t) + \int_0^t \left(\frac{M(\alpha(t))B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))(t-s)} + n(n+1) \right) V_n'(s) ds = \end{aligned}$$

$$= f_n(t) - n(n+1)\varphi_n + \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t}$$

$$V_n'(t) + \int_0^t \left(M(\alpha(t))e^{M(\alpha(t))(t-s)} + \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} n(n+1) \right) V_n'(s) ds =$$

$$= \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} \left(f_n(t) - n(n+1)\varphi_n + \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \right)$$

hosil bo'lgan tenglikdan

$$\tilde{f}_n(t) = \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} \left(f_n(t) - n(n+1)\varphi_n + \psi_n \frac{B(\alpha(t)-1)}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{M(\alpha(t))t} \right)$$

$$K(t,s) = M(\alpha(t))e^{M(\alpha(t))(t-s)} + \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} n(n+1)$$

kabi belgilash kiritsak, (10) tenglama quyidagi ikkinchi tur Volterra integral tenglamasiga keladi:

$$V_n'(t) + \int_0^t K(t,s)V_n'(s) ds = \tilde{f}_n(t) \quad (12)$$

yoki

$$V_n'(t) = \tilde{f}_n(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)V_n'(s) ds$$

$K(t,s)$ uzluksiz va $\tilde{f}_k(t)$ uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi bo'lsa, (12) tenglama yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

Endi hosil bo'lgan Volterra integral tenglamasini tadqiq etamiz. Biz integral tenglamaning rezolventasini topib, $V_n'(t)$ noma'lum funksiyaning yaqqol ko'rinishini topamiz. (12) tenglamani ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli yordamida ishlashga kirishamiz.

Nolinchi yaqinlashish sifatida $\tilde{f}(t)$ ni qabul qilamiz: ($V_n'(t) = \tilde{V}(t)$)

$$\tilde{V}_0(t) = \tilde{f}(t).$$

$\tilde{V}_1(t)$ ni esa

$$\tilde{V}_1(t) = \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)\tilde{f}(s) ds$$

munosabat bilan aniqlaymiz. Bu jarayonni davom ettirib,

$$\tilde{V}_n(t) = \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)\tilde{V}_{n-1}(s) ds$$

rekurrent formulani qanoatlantiruvchi

$$\tilde{V}_0(t), \tilde{V}_1(t), \dots, \tilde{V}_n(t), \dots$$

funksiyalarning cheksiz ketma ketligini hosil qilamiz.

Ikkinchi yaqinlashish

$$\tilde{V}_2(t) = \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)\tilde{V}_1(s)ds$$

formula bilan aniqlangani uchun, $\tilde{V}_1(s)$ ning o'rniga uning qiymatini qo'yib, Dirixle formulasidan foydalansak,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{V}_2(t) &= \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s) \left[\tilde{f}(s) - \int_0^s K(s,z)\tilde{f}(z)dz \right] ds = \\ &= \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)\tilde{f}(s)ds + \int_0^t K(t,s) \left[\int_0^s K(s,z)\tilde{f}(z)dz \right] ds = \\ &= \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t K(t,s)\tilde{f}(s)ds + \int_0^t \tilde{f}(z)dz \int_z^t K(t,s)K(s,z)ds \end{aligned}$$

tenglik hosil bo'ladi, bu yerda

$$K_2(t,z) = \int_z^t K(t,s)K(s,z)ds.$$

Xuddi shu yo'l bilan $\tilde{V}_n(t)$ uchun

$$\tilde{V}_n(t) = \tilde{f}(t) - \int_0^t \sum_{i=1}^n K(t,s)K_{i-1}(s,z)ds$$

formula hosil qilamiz, bunda

$$K_i(t,z) = \int_z^t K(t,s)K_{i-1}(s,z)ds.$$

Bizning tenglamda

$$K(t,s) = \frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}(t-s)} + \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} n(n+1).$$

Shu sababli yuqoridagi formuladan foydalansak, ikkinchi yaqinlashish quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$K_2(t, z) = \int_z^t \left(\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)} e^{\frac{\alpha(t)-1}{2-\alpha(t)}(t-s)} + \frac{2-\alpha(t)}{B(\alpha(t)-1)} n(n+1) \right) \times$$

$$\left(\frac{\alpha(s)-1}{2-\alpha(s)} e^{\frac{\alpha(s)-1}{2-\alpha(s)}(s-z)} + \frac{2-\alpha(s)}{B(\alpha(s)-1)} n(n+1) \right) ds$$

Xuddi shu tartibda davom etib, $V'_n(t)$ ni umumiy ko'rinishini rezolventa orqali ifodalab quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$V'_n(t) = \tilde{f}_n(t) - \int_0^t R(t, s) \tilde{f}_n(s) ds$$

Bu tenglikning har ikki tomonini integrallab, $V_n(t)$ ni yaqqol ko'rinishini quyidagicha topamiz:

$$V_n(t) = \int_0^t \tilde{f}_n(s) ds - \int_0^t \left(\int_0^s R(z, s) \tilde{f}_n(z) dz \right) ds + \varphi_n. \quad (13)$$

(13) ifodani (8) tengliklarga olib borib qo'yib, cheksiz qatorga ega bo'lamiz. Berilgan funksiyalarga ma'lum shatrlar asosida cheksiz qatorlarning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlaymiz.

Bizda quyidagi qator hosil bo'ladi.

$$U(x; t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^t \tilde{f}_n(s) ds - \int_0^t \left(\int_0^s R(z, s) \tilde{f}_n(z) dz \right) ds + \varphi_n \right) P_n(x). \quad (14)$$

$U(x; t)$ qatorni bahosini olamiz. Buning uchun $|U(x; t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |V_n(t)|$

tengsizlik bajarilishi kerak. Tengsizlikning o'ng tomonida qatnashgan qatorni yaqinlashuvchi bo'lishi uchun $V_n(t)$ da qatnashgan funksiyalarga ma'lum shatrlar tushadi. Buning uchun $V_1(t)$ ning ifodasidan foydalanamiz [3]:

$$V_1(t) = \int_0^t \tilde{f}_1(s) ds - \int_0^t \left(\int_0^s R(z, s) \tilde{f}_1(z) dz \right) ds + \varphi_1$$

$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_1}{n(n+1)}$ qator yaqinlashuvchi bo'lganli sababli,

$$|U(x; t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |V_n(t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_1}{n(n+1)}$$

yuqoridagi tengsizlik bajarilishini ta'minlasak (14) qatorni ham yaqinlashishini isbotlagan bo'lamiz. Buning uchun (14) qatorning tarkibida ishtirok

etayotgan $f_n(t)$ funksiya va φ_n, ψ_n Furye koeffitsiyentlarini bo'laklab integrallab, ko'rsatish mumkinki, ushbu

$$|U(x;t)| \leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} |V_n(t)| \leq \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_1}{n(n+1)} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_2 |\varphi_n^{(5)}|^2 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_3 |\psi_n^{(3)}|^2 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_4 |f_n^{(3)}|^2$$

tengsizlikning o'ng tomonidagi qatorlar yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi.

Tenglamada ishtirok etadigan $u_x, u_{xx}, {}^{CF}D_{0t}^{\alpha}u$ funksiyalarga mos keluvchi cheksiz qatorlarning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlashda berilgan $\varphi(x), f(x,t)$ funksiyalarga ko'proq shart tushishi tabiiy. Bunda [4] da ko'rsatilganidek hisoblashlar asosida $|g_n| \leq \frac{4\sqrt{2}}{(2n-3)^{3/2}} \|g\|$ tengsizliklardan foydalanamiz.

Masala yechimi yagonaligi esa Furye-Lejandr qatorlari nazariyasiga ko'ra Lejandr polinomlarining to'la ortonormal sistema tashkil qilishidan foydalanib isbotlanadi. Demak, quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli:

Teorema. Agar $\varphi(x) \in C^4[-1,1], \varphi^{(5)} \in L_2(-1,1), \varphi(-1) = \varphi(1) = 0,$
 $\varphi'(-1) = \varphi'(1) = 0, \varphi^4(-1) = \varphi^4(1) = 0, \psi \in C^2[-1,1], \psi''' \in L_2(-1,1), \psi(-1) = \psi(1) = 0,$
 $\psi''(-1) = \psi''(1) = 0, f(\cdot, t) \in C^2[-1,1], \frac{\partial^3 f}{\partial x^3}(\cdot, t) \in L_2(-1,1)$ shartlar bajarilsa, qo'yilgan masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagona bo'ladi.

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